

CHEMICAL EXPERIMENTS WITH CIGARETTES

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Annotation: It is well known that smoking is dangerous for human life, because tobacco smoke contains several thousand substances, among which there are quite a lot of harmful ones. To prove that tobacco smoke and tobacco contain substances harmful to health, as well as the negative role of tobacco smoking, we conducted the following experiments.

Keywords: omponents of smoke, consequences, tobacco lovers

Experience-1.

Obtaining solutions of substances contained in the smoke and filter of cigarettes Getting cigarette smoke and dissolving it. (The experiment was conducted under traction). The cigarette was fixed in the foot of the tripod and a rubber bulb was placed on it from the filter side. Squeezing a pear, they lit a cigarette and, creating a craving with the pear, they carefully unclenched it. At the same time, tobacco smoke fills the pear. 20-25 ml of distilled water was poured into a small glass and smoke was released from the pear into the water. To make the pear reach the bottom of the glass, put a glass tube on the pear. Some components of smoke dissolve in water. The sampling of cigarette smoke was repeated several times. Extraction of substances from a cigarette filter. We tore off the filter from the cigarette after "smoking", unwrapped it and placed it in a small flask with 20 ml of distilled water. The flask was stoppered and shaken several times.

The resulting solutions were left for subsequent experiments. Determination of the reaction of the medium of the obtained solutions. The reaction of the medium of the obtained solutions was investigated, for which a universal indicator paper was

added to them. It showed an acidic reaction of the environment. Acids are formed by the interaction of water with CO_2 , SO_2 and NO_2 , which are released during tobacco smoldering.:

Experience-2.

Detection of unsaturated compounds Pour 1 ml of solutions of substances contained in the smoke and filter of cigarettes into two test tubes and add 1-2 drops of iodine water (a few drops of pharmaceutical tincture of iodine are dissolved in 10 ml of water). Discoloration of solutions is observed:

Experience-3.

Comparison of tobacco products of different brands and identification of the relationship between permanganate oxidability and iodine number This part of the work consisted in comparing tobacco products of different brands and identifying the relationship between permanganate oxidability and iodine number (the amount of potassium permanganate and iodine, respectively, consumed for titrating a certain volume of tobacco extract) with the content of nicotine and tar in cigarettes [3]. To conduct the experiment, an installation was assembled consisting of a tripod with a foot, an ashtray, a stopper with a cigarette holder, a glass tube, a cotton swab and a connecting tube with a pear. The experiment was conducted with various types of tobacco products. After preparing the extract for all analyzed cigarettes and for their filters, they were quantified according to two criteria: the iodine number and permanganate oxidizability. Titration of tobacco extract was carried out on an installation consisting of a tripod with a foot, a chemical glass and a burette for titration. For permanganometry, 10 ml of tobacco extract was taken and titrated with a solution of potassium permanganate of known concentration until a red-pink color appeared. This method is indicator-free, as the color is given by potassium

permanganate itself. Iodometry was performed by titrating 10 ml of tobacco extract with a solution of iodine of a certain concentration in the presence of starch until a stable blue color appeared due to the formation of a complex of excess iodine with starch. The results of the determination are presented in Table 1. Based on the assumption that the relationship between the iodine number and permanganate oxidability and the content of harmful substances in tobacco smoke is directly proportional, we have compiled a comparative series of different brands of tobacco products in terms of the content of harmful substances in them: Maxim > Optima > Winston > West > More > Camel > "PallMall" > "Chesterfield".

Brand of tobacco products	$v(I_2) \times 10^{-4}$, mole		$v(KMnO_4) \times 10^{-3}$, mole	
	tobacco smoke	tobacco smoke filter	tobacco smoke filter	filter
«Chesterfield»	8,66	30,3	7,59	22,02
«PallMall»	8,66	17,3	9,1	18,99
«Camel»	12,99	21,66	9,1	19,75
«More»	17,3	12,99	8,35	15,94
«West»	21,66	17,3	12,1	18,99
«Winston»	25,9	17,3	12,9	19,75
«Оптимa»	34,6	12,99	12,9	14,43
«Максим»	34,6	12,99	14,4	12,9

Currently, smoking has become a massive epidemic in our country, which has spread not only among men and women, but also among teenagers, which is a significant threat to the health of citizens. Smoking is the most common bad habit in our country. Currently, 65% of men and up to 30% of women smoke. Smoking begins in adolescence. There are also a lot of teenagers who smoke at the school where I study. Everyone knows the consequences of smoking: heart disease, chronic bronchitis, lung cancer, laryngeal cancer, etc. Thus, the problem of combating

smoking is very relevant and its solution primarily depends on the consciousness of the people themselves. I care about the fate of my friends, I want to communicate with them, but I don't want to be a passive smoker. Therefore, I decided to confirm in practice the harmful effects of cigarettes on living organisms, to familiarize students of my school with the results of my work, so that they value their health and the health of others.

when a person touches a cigarette for the first time, he does not think about the serious consequences that smoking can lead to. After the first puff, nicotine appears in the brain tissues after 7 seconds. Nicotine improves communication between brain cells, facilitating the conduction of nerve impulses. Brain processes are temporarily stimulated by nicotine, but then they are inhibited for a long time. After all, the brain needs rest. By shifting the usual pendulum of mental activity, the smoker then inevitably feels its reverse course. The respiratory organs are the first to take on the tobacco attack. And they suffer most often. Passing through the respiratory tract, tobacco smoke causes irritation and inflammation of the mucous membranes of the pharynx, nasopharynx, trachea, bronchi, and pulmonary alveoli. Constant irritation of the bronchial mucosa can trigger the development of bronchial asthma. And chronic inflammation of the upper respiratory tract, chronic bronchitis, accompanied by a debilitating cough, is the lot of all smokers. Damage to the heart and blood vessels in people who smoke a lot and systematically is a consequence of a violation of the regulation of the cardiovascular system. Hypertensive disease is much more severe in tobacco lovers than in non-smokers: it is more often complicated by hypertensive crises, and stroke is a violation of cerebral circulation. Smoking is one of the main causes of the development of such a serious disease as obliterating endarteritis. In this disease, the vascular system of the legs is affected, sometimes up to a complete narrowing of the vascular lumen (obliteration) and the appearance of gangrene. Smoking impairs human hearing to the same extent as aging of the body. Even 20 cigarettes smoked per day lead to a weakening of the normal perception of

spoken language. Smoking has a detrimental effect on a pregnant woman. During pregnancy, the negative effects of smoking manifest themselves much faster, and especially in relation to a developing child. It has been shown that if the mother smoked during pregnancy, the newborn's weight is 150-200 grams less than normal. Smokers endanger not only themselves, but also the people around them. There is a term "Secondhand smoke" - the inhalation of ambient air with tobacco products contained in it by other people. A significant concentration of nicotine is detected in the body of non-smokers after staying in a smoky and unventilated room.

Experience-4.

Qualitative reaction to aldehydes Methodology: I poured 2 ml of tobacco smoke solution from flasks No. 2 and No. 3 into two test tubes, added 5 drops of 5% KMnO_4 solution to each tube, and shook the tubes slightly. Result: The KMnO_4 solution discolored, and a brown MnO_2 precipitate fell out as a result of the reaction. Conclusion: Tobacco smoke contains reducing agents that are highly toxic and irritating. These are benzaldehyde, formaldehyde, and acrolein. When these substances interact with a KMnO_4 solution in a neutral medium, a brown MnO_2 precipitate precipitates due to the reduction of KMnO_4 by substances contained in tobacco smoke. The amount of harmful substances in a solution of tobacco smoke from a cigarette with a filter is less than in a solution of a cigarette without a filter. Therefore, the MnO_2 precipitate is formed more in a test tube with a solution from flask No. 3. Some of the harmful substances are trapped by the cigarette filter.

Experimentally, I became convinced that tobacco smoke really contains a lot of chemicals that have a detrimental effect on living organisms. In the process of doing the work, I learned a lot of things that I didn't know before. Of course, I've read about the negative effects of smoking and I know about it from parents and teachers. But the work has not only enriched me with new knowledge and skills, but also with new impressions, inspired me to fight smoking among the children and other people.

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